

OSeMOSYS step - a python package for modelling energy systems under limited foresight and with decision trees

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Abstract.

A common challenge in energy system optimisation models is the representation of investment decision patterns. Such capacity expansion models often assume perfect foresight. Thereby they assume certainty for the entire modelling horizon. This produces investment patterns that are cost optimal on the long-term but not necessarily for single assets on the short-term. Therefore, models with limited foresight can provide valuable insights when trying to anticipate investment patterns in the power sector. This article presents a Python package that expands the capabilities of the Open Source energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to facilitate modelling with limited foresight. Furthermore, it applies the package to investigate the impact of foresight horizon length on the accumulated CO₂ emissions in a decarbonisation scenario and investigates the possibilities to model disruptive events.

To expand the functionality of OSeMOSYS, a fully open Python package is developed that allows the user to run a provided model with limited foresight. The model time horizon is divided into multiple independently cost-optimised time steps with the option to vary parameters between time steps to represent decisions or disruptive events. The package allows to run decision trees by providing multiple data options for model parameters. The decision tree then incorporates all possible combinations of the provided options.

The article shows for the case of a decarbonisation scenario that a shortening of the foresight horizon leads to an increase in CO₂ emissions accumulated over the modelling horizon. This illustrates the importance of analysing and considering foresight horizon lengths at different levels of decision making in policy design.

The analysis of model results when applying the decision tree feature illustrate that OSeMOSYS_step facilitates to model sudden and disruptive events while keeping limited foresight. This allows for analysis of the robustness of the energy system to deal with sudden changes in the boundary conditions.

Keywords: investment cycles; myopia; long-term planning; decision trees; decisions.

1. Introduction

Over the last decade a landscape of open-source energy system planning models has emerged [1]. Their scope and functionality vary from long-term investment planning [2] down to unit dispatch models [3]. While there are many forms and approaches to represent time in these models, one can distinguish between models that study investment decisions over long time periods and multiple years, and models that study operational decisions over shorter time periods ($\tilde{1}$ year or less). In the former group a central aspect of interest are the investment patterns over the years, commonly studied through linear cost optimisation programs.

For such long-term investment planning models, an important design aspect of the modelling system is if the model is optimising the investments over the modelled time horizon in one go or in several iterations. A common choice is to assume perfect foresight (PF). PF means that the optimisation of investments and operation is performed for the entire modelling period as a whole. The optimisation assumes complete certainty for the data provided, including developments far in the future, for example cost trajectories, demand developments, and weather forecasts. However, in reality an important factor for investment decisions is the profitability of an investment in the near-term future, for which costs and revenue are with relatively high certainty foreseeable. Therefore, investment patterns in models assuming PF might not reflect real world observations [4].

Many studies have developed methods to investigate the impacts of PF on model results. Keppo et al. analyse the effects of limited foresight using a global scale MESSAGE model. They highlight how limited foresight delays and misleads investment decisions early in the modelling period and how this leads to higher cost later in the modelling period [4]. Heuberger et al. first define the difference between PF, myopia, and myopia with limited foresight. Myopia means that a model is split into steps of a defined length and each step is optimised separately. Myopia with limited foresight also splits the model into steps, but the model of each step contains some years that go beyond the years in the step and of which the results are discarded. These years are referred to as foresight horizon. Heuberger et al. then investigate the implications of policy makers waiting for a unicorn technology, which they define as a technology that is not yet commercially available but that is CO_2 emission free, low in capital and operational cost, and can provide ancillary services, instead of taking action using existing technologies. They compare the results for these two approaches in a setting with PF and myopia with limited foresight using the ESO modelling framework [5]. Fuso-Nerini et al. use the UK TIMES (UKTM) model to investigate the mismatch between the planned decarbonisation pathway for the UK and the actual pathway taken by decision makers based on short-term analysis. They show that the postponement and potential technology lock-ins could lead to significant cost increases to reach the decarbonisation targets [6]. Poncelet et al. investigate in detail what insights myopic optimisation models can provide in regards to investment decisions in liberalised energy

market and where the limitations of myopic optimisation models lie using a model inspired by the Belgian power sector. They note that a combination of myopia and stochastic modelling could be interesting [7]. More recently, Sitarz et al. compared model results from a PF and a myopic set-up to illustrate how the two set-ups together can facilitate the explanation of real-world observations of the emissions price in the European Union (EU) Emissions Trading System (ETS) [8]. They show that the ability to switch between a PF and a myopic setup expands the range of possible analyses for modelling frameworks. The study provides highly relevant insights for policy makers and underlines the importance of modelling frameworks having both a PF and a myopic setup. Common across these four studies is the finding that myopic model runs can illustrate investment patterns that reflect short to medium term revenue oriented investment decision which might contradict cost optimal decision to reach long-term policy targets. Beyond the here mentioned modelling frameworks and their myopic applications, also the electricity system model GenX and the Energy System Optimisation Model (ESOM) PyPSA provide the functionality to run under myopia [9, 10]. None of the afore mentioned modelling studies or frameworks include the ability to implement decisions by parameter options in between the steps of a myopic model. This feature allows to model decision options, but also the impact of probability distributions of parameters on the model results.

In this paper we present a Python package that allows to run models build in the Open Source energy Modelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS) in a myopic set-up with limited foresight and branching decision trees (DTs). OSeMOSYS is a fully open-source long-term energy planning modelling framework and has been widely applied in energy planning and capacity building measures in developing countries [11].

To demonstrate the capabilities of OSeMOSYS_step, we investigate two research questions. First, we investigate the impact of the length of the foresight horizon has on the results of a power system investment model. And second, we investigate how the modelling of DTs affects the decisions and results of a power system model, especially whether the DT feature facilitates the modelling of sudden and disruptive events. For the investigation of these questions we use the European power sector model OSeMBE, a model built in OSeMOSYS. Above we highlighted that numerous other energy investment planning frameworks comprise the functionality to run in a myopic setting. However, the OSeMOSYS framework was missing this feature up until now. Furthermore, the possibility to run DTs improves the possibility to run scenario and sensitivity analysis' in OSeMOSYS.

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows; section 2 describes the methods and functionalities implemented in OSeMOSYS_step, section 3 presents two use cases, section 4 discusses and reflects on the results from the use cases, and section 5 contains the conclusion and assesses the scientific contribution of the paper and potential future work.

2. Methods

In this section we have two main sub-sections. In the first subsection we present the functionalities that OSeMOSYS_step contains. In the second subsection programmatic implementation is presented.

2.1. Functionalities

In this section we describe the functions and options that the OSeMOSYS_step package provides. OSeMOSYS_step provides two main functions. Firstly, it allows the user to run an OSeMOSYS model under limited foresight, with a user-configurable step length. Secondly, it provides the option to run a DT using an OSeMOSYS model, this implies that also here the model is run under limited foresight. The DT feature allows for the modelling of sudden and disruptive events.

The package converts the default OSeMOSYS PF problem into a problem under myopia with limited foresight by splitting the provided model into a series of sequential sub-models of user defined length. Among the years in the sub-models we can distinguish between years that are part of the step which are reporting into the final results, and the years that represent the foresight horizon, but which are not reported in the final results, this is illustrated in the upper half of Figure 1 where the solid lines indicate the years that are part of a step and the dotted lines the years in the foresight horizon. The length of the step and the length of the foresight horizon are user defined. The results of the steps are merged after running all steps and provide insights over the full model horizon.

Additionally, OSeMOSYS_step allows the user to provide multiple values for one or more parameters between steps. These options can represent decisions, but could also represent selected values of a discrete probability distribution. The provision of such options allows the user to define DTs, providing only one model data set and the options for selected parameters. It is possible to provide options for several parameters or sets of parameters at the same time, i.e., representing multiple decisions. OSeMOSYS_step then automatically runs all possible combinations in the DT. Therefore, the number of scenarios can rise quickly. Hence, it is important to carefully plan the number of decisions and options provided. The DT feature allows to model sudden and disruptive events. It allows for this by using the data of the provided model in all steps including the foresight horizon, till the decision implemented. A simple DT is provided in Figure 2. It illustrates how the provision of a decision creates scenarios. The number of branches at the bottom of the figure illustrate the number of possible scenarios based on all possible combinations of the options provided for the different decisions in Figure 2. In Figure 1 we illustrate the difference between scenarios run under PF (lower part of the figure) and a DT run with myopia and limited foresight. In the representation of the decision tree under myopia with limited foresight the step is indicated by a continuous line while the foresight horizon is indicated by a dotted line. The figure illustrates how the sub-models that are created by OSeMOSYS_step are overlapping in their time horizon, but that only

Figure 1: Comparison of scenarios when running models with perfect foresight and limited foresight.

the results of the years in the step are considered while for the years in the foresight horizon the next sub-model is providing the results. Via the colourful diamonds Figure 1 also illustrates how running scenarios under myopia with limited foresight allows to model sudden events. In a perfect foresight setting events and decisions are anticipated since the entire modelling period is optimised at once, see lower half of Figure 1. In contrast in the myopic set-up with limited foresight, the step-wise optimisation prevents the anticipation of sudden events and thereby might give more insightful results on the implications of sudden paradigm shifts or similar. OSeMOSYS_step also allows the user to specify the solver to use. The current implementation allows to solve the models with the open-source solvers GLPK and CBC, but also the commercial solvers Gurobi and Cplex, which are free of charge for academic users.

2.2. Implementation

The OSeMOSYS_step package is coded in Python and allows for any number of user defined decisions. This section will describe the code workflow, the file management structure, and how users interface with the package.

2.2.1. User Interaction At a minimum, the user must provide OSeMOSYS_step with an OSeMOSYS model file (containing the code of the OSeMOSYS linear program), a data file, and a corresponding otoole configuration file. The OSeMOSYS model defines the parameters, variables, sets, and constraints within the model (for example, see the base OSeMOSYS model). OSeMOSYS is an open-source tool, therefore many versions of the code exist for different research questions. The modeller is free to provide any version of the OSeMOSYS model code, provided it is written in GNU MathProg [12]. The set and parameter data to accompany the model file are provided in a single MathProg text file, which shares syntax with the AMPL language. To perform the data conversions and result processing, the python package otoole (OSeMOSYS Tools for Energy Work) is used; otoole requires a configuration file defining all the sets, parameters, and variables in the model [13].

When provided with the above indicated inputs OSeMOSYS_step will break the model from a PF model into a series of sequential models with limited foresight. To determine the length of each step, upon calling the workflow, the modeller provides a *step_length* argument. This argument indicates the number of years in each step; which can, for example, represent political terms in office when energy policies are introduced, cancelled, or renewed. The total number of steps in the model is determined by dividing the number of years in the model horizon by the number of years per step. In the case that the division produces a remainder, the last years of the model horizon constitute a shorter step. However, it is also possible to provide a different length for the first step, compared to the remaining steps. See GitHub documentation for use cases.

To use the DT functionality, the user must additionally to the above listed inputs provide the data describing the options for the decisions to be made in each step. If decision data is provided, the package automatically creates branches at the step for which the decision is provided and for all following steps. Table 1 shows an example of how the data for a decision can be structured. In this specific case the decision of allowing or banning nuclear investments in 2000 and onwards is shown. The time dependent parameter is added under the "PARAMETER" heading, the region to apply the option to is added under the "REGION" heading, and the technology associated with the parameter is added under the "TECHNOLOGY" heading. If only one decision is provided, each option under the "OPTION" heading represents a new branch in the DT. If multiple decisions are provided the package will create branches for all possible combinations of the decision options provided. In the example in Table 1 the decision has two options which creates a two branch DT, as illustrated in 2. In option zero, the model does not have investment restrictions on nuclear power, while in option one, the model can not invest in any nuclear power. For each step, the modeller can define as many different decisions with as many different options as they like; however, they should be cautious of the number of model runs this will correspond to.

2.2.2. Results Structure As described above, OSeMOSYS_step breaks the provided OSeMOSYS model into a series of consecutive sub-models. The output of the package

Figure 2: UTOPIA, one decision, two options, illustration of decision in Table 2

Table 1: Example Decision Option Data

PARAMETER	REGION	TECH.	OPTION	YEAR	VALUE
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	0	2000	-1
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	0	2001	-1
		...			
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	0	2009	-1
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	0	2010	-1
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	1	2000	0
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	1	2001	0
		...			
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	1	2009	0
TotalAnnualMax-CapacityInvestment	UTOPIA	NUCLEAR	1	2010	0

Table 2: Example options for scenario and options. This setup describes an emission policy (scenario E) that implements three different emission penalties; no penalty, a moderate penalty, and an aggressive penalty (option 0, 1, 2 respectively). In both steps 1 and 3, the emission policy can change. Moreover, a binary technology investment decision (such as allowing or disallowing nuclear investment) occurs in steps 2 and 3 (option 0 and 1 respectively). This represents a structure with $3 \times 2 \times 3 \times 2 = 36$ options

Step	Decision	Options
1	E	0,1,2
2	T	0,1
3	E	0,1,2
3	T	0,1

are results for each scenario possible based on the combinations of provided decision options, only scenarios that are infeasible are skipped and remain without results. For each of the scenarios the results cover the full model horizon of the model provided as input to OSeMOSYS_step. In version XXX OSeMOSYS_step provides the results within a nested folder structure. The folder structure contains for each scenario a set of CSV-files with the OSeMOSYS-results variables.

The naming of scenarios and the related directories happens automatically in OSeMOSYS_step. In the following we describe how the directories containing the scenario results are named in version XXX of OSeMOSYS_step. To do so we use a more complex example than above. Table 2 shows a set of four decisions in three steps. The decisions have two and three options, which creates a total of 36 scenarios. The corresponding DT is illustrated in Figure 3.

The corresponding directories would be named following a 3 index code structure. The first index will give the step number, the second index will give the decision name, and the third index will give the option number. Each step where a new scenario is implemented will create a new sub-directory. If multiple decisions are applied in a single step, the code is separated by a dash.

For example, the directory structure following the example presented above is shown in Figure 4. The directory *"results/1E0/2T0/3E1-3T0/"* will contain the results for the option of no emission penalty in the first step (*1E0*), banning nuclear investment in the second step (*2T0*), then implementing a moderate emission penalty while retaining the nuclear ban in the third step (*3E1-3T0*). As will be explained in the subsequent section, if a model run fails (due to over constraining the system), all results for the the model run are removed. For example, if restricting nuclear investment breaks the model (possibly due to a requirement to invest in nuclear imposed in the master data file), all runs under the *T20/* directories are removed.

Figure 3: Example option decision tree, accompanying Table 2

Figure 4: Result directory structure following the example presented in Table 2 and Figure 3. The results for the 36 scenarios will be stored in the last sub-directory folder (i.e. 3E0-3T0, 3E0-3T1, ...)

Table 3: Input Arguments to the workflow

Input Argument	Restrictions	Optional	Description	Default
step_length	Must be integer	No	The number of years in each step	n/a
input_data	Must be a path to a *.txt file	No	The input MathProg data file	n/a
solver	Must be one of "glpk", "cbc", "gurobi"	Yes	Solver used. Defaults to CBC	CBC
cores	Must be an integer	Yes	Number of cores to solve the model with	1
foresight	Must be integer	Yes	Number of years that each step has as foresight horizon	n/a
path_param	Must be a path to a directory	Yes	Location to save result data	results/

2.2.3. Workflow Logic The flowchart of the process underlying OSeMOSYS_step can be found in Figure 5. In the following we highlight the main steps of the process. Firstly, the user provides input options through the command line when calling the OSeMOSYS_step package. All arguments that can be provided to the current version of the package are described in Table 3. In the first step the package creates the directory structure for model data and results based on the input provided for scenarios and step length. In the following steps the provided model datafile is first converted to a set of CSV-files and then, using the provided step length, split into sub-models with a model time horizon covering by default twice the step length, see Equation 2. In case the input argument *foresight* is provided, the model horizon consists of step length plus *foresight*. Next, the scenario data as described in Table 1 is applied sequentially to each step-problem, see first yellow diamond in Figure 5.

$$YearsPerStep_{Reported} = StepLength \quad (1)$$

$$YearsPerStep_{Modelled} = StepLength \times 2 \quad (2)$$

Once all data has been parsed, the main loop begins which builds and solves all models in step-by-step. First, solver agnostic Linear Programming (LP) files are created for each model. The workflow management tool, Snakemake [14], is used to solve each model in a step in parallel. Once solutions are obtained, otool [15] is used to convert an unformatted solution file (.sol) into a suite of CSV result files. From these result files the results for the years within the current step are appended to the overall results of the corresponding scenario (see Figure 4). Lastly, the newly installed capacity in one step is passed into the subsequent steps as existing capacity, as represented in Figure 6. The loop exits if the last step is reached.

3. Use Cases

In this section we present two use cases of OSeMOSYS_step to illustrate its functionality and discuss the impact of myopia with limited foresight on the model results. In the two use cases a net-zero scenario implemented in the OSeMBE model is used. The OSeMBE model has been described in detail by Henke et al. [16]. It has a model horizon from 2015 to 2050. The net-zero scenario has been developed in the H2020 project European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMF) [17] and has been described by [18]. The scenario reaches at a global level zero GHG emissions in 2050. In OSeMBE, which models the European power sector only, this implies an emission reduction trajectory with negative CO_2 emissions in 2050.

3.1. Use Case 1: The impact of the foresight horizon

In the first use case we explore running OSeMOSYS models under myopia with limited foresight using OSeMOSYS_step. We investigate what kind of analysis the option to provide a user-defined length of the foresight horizon allows.

3.1.1. Use case 1 - Design In this use case we compare the results of the net-zero scenario when run in three different set-ups. All three set-ups are using the same net-zero scenario, but we run the scenario three times, first with PF, second under myopia and limited foresight with a step length of five years and 20 years foresight, and third under myopia and limited foresight with a step length of five years and 5 years foresight.

3.1.2. Use case 1 - Results In this section we compare the three set-ups described above. As a first metric of comparison we look at the annual CO_2 emissions in the model, illustrated in Figure 7. In blue we see the PF set-up, the conventional OSeMOSYS set-up. The red and green line show the runs using OSeMOSYS_step and applying myopia with limited foresight. In both cases the step length is 5 years. Very notable in Figure

Figure 5: Workflow flowchart

Figure 6: Process for carrying over residual capacity into subsequent model runs

Figure 7: CO₂ emissions in use case 1 in scenarios run with perfect foresight or limited foresight of 5 or 20 years

(a) Coal power generation in use case 1 in scenarios with and without Carbon Capture and Storage after 2040, run with perfect foresight or limited foresight of 5 or 20 years

(b) Gas power generation in use case 1 in scenarios with and without Carbon Capture and Storage after 2040, run with perfect foresight or limited foresight

Figure 8: Development of power generation by coal and gas across scenarios in use case 1

7 are the emissions in the set-up under myopia with only 5 years of foresight, shown by the green line. Between 2021 and 2038 they are clearly higher than the emissions of the other scenarios. And also after 2038 the green line remains almost till 2050 higher than the blue line, which is representing the scenario under PF. The scenario with 20 years foresight shows overall only small differences to the PF scenario. In some periods, e.g., 2024-2029, the emissions are slightly higher than in the PF set-up.

To understand where the differences in emissions in Figure 7 originate, we look at the power generation from coal in Figure 8a. We observe a comparable pattern to the emission trajectories in Figure 7. While the PF set-up and the 20 years foresight set-up results are almost completely in line, the five years foresight set-up generates significantly more electricity from coal. This explains the increased CO_2 emissions between 2021 and 2035. In all three set-ups the power generation by coal ends in 2039. Therefore, the differences in emissions after that year must have a different origin. In Figure 8b we therefore look at the power generation from natural gas. While the usage of coal for power generation is significantly more affected if the foresight horizon is set to 5 years, and only little by a foresight horizon of 20 years, the power generation by natural gas shows very different patterns, see Figure 8b. The overall pattern, a spike in power generation by gas in the years 2023 and 2024, and a plateau between 2038 and 2050, remains the same across all set-ups, however, we see notable differences in the amount of electricity generated by gas. After a low in power generation by gas around 2030 a strong growth in all set-ups can be observed. The growth is stronger the shorter the foresight horizon is. However, after peaking highest between 2038 and 2040 the 5 year foresight horizon set-up drops its gas usage below the one of the scenario with 20 years foresight in 2044 and remains lower until the end of the modelling period. After

Figure 9: Power generation by energy carrier across scenarios in 2020, 2030, 2040, and 2050 in Use Case 1

2050 the usage of natural gas for power generation decreases in all scenarios.

In Figure 9 we set the observations from Figure 8 into context of the overall power generation and compare the power generation across the three set-ups for the years 2020, 2030, 2040, and 2050 to further investigate how the different foresight horizons affect the model results. We observe that the energy carriers are affected differently. The use of coal that we already analysed above, is among the more strongly affected energy carriers. However, coal is phased out before 2040. Beyond coal, most strongly affected by the foresight horizon are the use of gas, nuclear, offshore wind, and onshore wind. While gas and offshore wind are increasingly used with shorter foresight horizons, the use of nuclear and onshore wind decreases. The decreased use of nuclear power and the increased use of coal and gas falls in line with results by [4, 7]. It relates to the ratio of investment cost and operational cost. The investment cost of nuclear power is in comparison high, while the investment cost for gas power plants is in comparison low. Therefore, the model invests, when using a set-up with a short foresight horizon less into nuclear power and more into gas fired power plants in the early years of the modelling period. However, on the medium term also in the set-up with 5 years foresight the models starts investing into nuclear power, but due to limits on the annual investment into nuclear it cannot install sufficient nuclear capacity to satisfy the electricity demand. Therefore, we can observe in Figure 9 a lower share of nuclear power in the 5-year foresight set-up in 2040 and 2050 than in the other set-ups and a higher share of offshore wind power.

The changes in the power generation mix and the related changes investments affect also the annual investment in the power sector, this is illustrated in Figure 10. We can observe that the PF set-up (blue) and the 20-year foresight set-up (red) have a very

Figure 10: The total capital investment over the modelled time horizon in the use-case 1 scenarios

similar investment patterns. Only in the first half of the model horizon the investments vary in some years. In contrast, the set-up with 5-years foresight (green) has already in the first half of the modelling period a deviating investment pattern from the perfect foresight scenario, with partly higher but also repeatedly lower investments. These differences lead in the long-term to a higher investment need. After 2037 the 5-year foresight set-up has consistently higher investment requirements than the PF and the 20-year foresight scenario, with exception of the year 2040.

3.2. Use Case 2: Parameter options and decision trees

In the second use case we illustrate how decisions at defined points in time affect the results, how these decisions affect the solution, and what possibilities this feature creates.

3.2.1. Use case 2 - Design In this second use case we use the same decarbonisation scenario implemented in OSeMBE as the one used in use case 1. However, in contrast to use case 1 we make use of the OSeMOSYS_step feature to model decisions and implement the availability of CCS as a decision in 2040. The input model to OSeMOSYS_step has CCS available after 2040 like in use case 1, but in 2040 the decision can be made to keep CCS banned, thereby creating an alternative sub-scenario.

We compare the results generated with the DT function in OSeMOSYS_step with the results from the myopic scenario runs from use case 1. We drop the PF set-up from the comparison, since Figure 7 shows that there is not much difference in emissions between the PF set-up and the limited foresight set-up with 20 years foresight. Among

(a) Overall CO_2 emissions in use case 2

(b) CO_2 emissions in use case 2, zoom in on the years 2035 till 2040

Figure 11: CO_2 emissions in use case 2 in scenarios with and without Carbon Capture and Storage after 2040, run with limited foresight of 20 years

the set-ups with limited foresight we select the set-up with 20 years foresight for the comparison.

3.2.2. Use case 2 - Results In Figure 11 we show results for the two sub-scenarios run once with DT feature and once independently in the myopic set-up. The sub-scenarios run with the DT feature are shown in red. In these sub-scenarios the model anticipates till 2040 that CCS will become available. The sub-scenarios without DT function are shown in blue, here the final decision outcome is anticipated once 2040 and the following years come into the foresight horizon. The scenarios without CCS have solid lines and those with CCS are dotted. Until 2035 all scenarios are hidden under the red line of the scenario without CCS run with the DT feature. However, then, five years before the CCS becomes available in some of the sub-scenarios the graphs diverge. While the sub-scenario with CCS and run without the DT feature is constantly hidden below the red and red dotted lines, the other three sub-scenarios are all visible between 2035 and 2040. Therefore, we zoom into this area of the plot in Figure 11b. In solid blue and solid red we see the scenarios without CCS. It is interesting to observe that they are not in line for these years. The facts that the solid red line follows the pattern of the sub-scenarios in which CCS becomes available shows that the DT feature facilitates the modelling of sudden events. In 2039 the red dotted line of the scenario with CCS run with the DT feature appears from below the red line and dives downwards. It is covering the blue dotted line of the scenario with CCS run without the DT feature. In both sub-scenarios emissions had increased in the years before CCS became available, because the model anticipated the availability of CCS after 2039 and avoided investments into other technologies.

The dotted lines of the sub-scenarios with CCS illustrate that the DT feature produces the same results for a provided model as when run without the DT feature.

Figure 12: Development of power generation from natural gas with 20 years foresight, comparing scenarios using and not using the decision tree feature

Whereas the solid red line shows that the alternatives provided as decisions in the DT feature create different results. The sub-scenario without CCS run with the DT feature overlays the scenarios with CCS until 2039 because in its foresight horizon it anticipates that CCS will be available. Hence it makes the same investment decisions as the scenarios that have CCS available from 2040 onwards. But since CCS does not become available in 2040, the red scenario then aligns with the other no-CCS scenario.

The effect caused by the DT feature is also noticeable in the power generation by natural gas, shown in Figure 12. It is visible how in 2039 the solid red line of the no-CCS run with DT sub-scenario leaves the red dotted line representing the scenario with-CCS and from 2040 onwards runs below the sub-scenarios with CCS show by the dotted lines and above the sub-scenario without CCS run without the DT feature, shown by the solid blue line. The difference between solid red line and solid blue line illustrates the difference in gas usage due to the avoided anticipation of the sudden event when using the DT feature.

4. Discussion

In this section we discuss the results presented in the previous sections regarding their implications, how they compare to the existing literature, and where they add to the literature.

Poncelet et al. and Keppo and Strubegger find that a myopic setting in investment planning models leads to increased greenhouse gas emissions, due to changed investment

patterns [7, 4]. In use case 1 we confirm these findings. We observe that the model is more prone to use CO_2 emitting technologies, since it does not anticipate the increasing cost related to the emissions. In the early years of the modelling period the model uses more coal power and in later years more gas power, when a setting with limited foresight is used. This confirmation of the findings of previous studies is relevant, because, in contrast to those previous studies, we use a scenario with a price trajectory for CO_2 leading globally to net-zero emissions in 2050.

To answer the question of the effect of the decision tree feature on the results of the model, we investigate in use case 2 how the results for the decision on CCS availability from 2040 onwards using the decision tree feature differ from the results when running the two options separately. In the corresponding results comparison, we show that the decision tree feature allows for the investigation of sudden and disruptive events. In the results comparison we observe how the results of the sub-scenario for which the data differs from the provided model follow the results of the provided model till 2040, the year of the decision, and then deviate. In contrast, when the data for the sub-scenario is part of the model data from the beginning, no matter if in a PF set-up or a set-up with limited foresight, the results start deviating before the decision year. This finding indicates that the DT feature allows the investigation of sudden and disruptive events with OSeMOSYS models. Such events could be policy decision, natural catastrophes, or technological breakthroughs. The investigation of such events allows to generate insights on the robustness of the energy system and the economic efficiency, for example whether the system is still able to serve expected demands after a disruption and at what cost, and if investments are useful for the energy system across scenarios or just under specific boundary conditions that might change.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion we can note that this paper presents three additions to the scientific literature.

Firstly, we present a Python package to run OSeMOSYS models, which by default assume perfect foresight, under myopia with limited foresight. The OSeMOSYS_step package expands the possibilities of analysis for all OSeMOSYS models that use a model file in GNU MathProg. For facilitating the use of OSeMOSYS models not using a GNU MathProg version of OSeMOSYS, the scripts handling the running process would need to be expanded.

The possibility to conduct analysis using a limited foresight setting and comparing it with results under perfect foresight is particularly interesting since OSeMOSYS is frequently used for capacity development in developing countries [11]. Since long-term planning processes in developing countries are often facing the challenge of a lack of infrastructure and data [19], it could be of particular interest in such cases to investigate and highlight the possible implications of myopic planning. But as highlighted in section 1, also in developed countries myopic investment decisions are challenge for

decarbonisation efforts. OSeMOSYS_step provides a tool that allows to analyse why myopic investment decisions occur and thereby facilitates the development of strategies to prevent or at least deal with such investments.

Secondly, OSeMOSYS_step provides functionality for user defined foresight horizon. In use case 1, see section 3.1, we illustrated how the length of the foresight horizon impacts the model results. We are able to show that also with a CO_2 price trajectory that at the global level should lead to net-zero emissions by 2050, the amount of emissions throughout the modelling period increases the shorter the length of the foresight horizon. This underlines the relevance of investigating the consequences of short-sighted decisions making and developing strategies how to prevent short-sighted investments. In future studies, the possibility to vary the length of the foresight horizon could be used to investigate the implications of different planning horizons at different levels of decision making, e.g. a policy maker might have a different planning horizon than an investor. At the policy making level the gained insights could feed into better policy design that anticipates decision motives at other decision making levels.

Thirdly, the possibility to run DTs, using the DT feature, opens the possibility to investigate the implications of political paradigm shifts and natural catastrophes. In use case 2, see section 3.2, we illustrate that the DT feature overcomes the foresight related issue that developments are anticipated and hence reflected in the results of the model. With the DT feature, the model anticipates a future that is then changed at a user-defined point in time. This allows for example to investigate sudden political paradigm shifts or changes in availability fuel and their effect on the energy system.

Furthermore, we can note that the set-up of OSeMOSYS_step has similarities to a stochastic model set-up, as they can be found in modelling frameworks like TIMES [20] or TEMOA [21]. However, in stochastic modelling parameter options are commonly associated with a probability which allows to determine probabilities for the different scenarios of a DT. OSeMOSYS_step however does currently not allow stochastic model runs since it does not incorporate the handling of probabilities. Due to the similarities in structure, this could be a future development of the package.

Lastly, there is a use case of the OSeMOSYS_step package that has not been investigated in this paper. The package has been designed for the run models under myopia with limited foresight with or without making use of the DT feature. However, if a step length that is equal to the model horizon length is provided, the package also facilitates model runs under perfect foresight while considering option data. To do so the package needs to be provided with a reference case data file, decision options for step 0, and a step length equal to the length of the modelling period. The package then runs the model with perfect foresight while implementing the provided decision options. This use case is interesting for organising the maintenance and further development of models. For example when dealing with a set of scenarios, having one reference model and the scenario deviation as option data would ease the updating of the model since only one data set would need to be modified and not multiple data sets for each scenario.

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7. Contributions

H. H. conducted the literature review, the conceptualisation of code and article, programmed the the first version of the scripts, the formal analysis and wrote the majority original manuscript. T. B. revised and updated the code, wrote sections of the original manuscript, and reviewed the article. W. U. reviewed the original article and contributed to packaging the code to a Python package.

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